

SYNERGISTIC DAMAGE MECHANICS MODELING OF FAILURE IN MULTIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Abstract

Presently, composite structures are designed against strength failure. The criteria used are often empirical and overly conservative. A series of World-Wide Failure Exercises (WWFEs) have been conducted to compare and analyze different failure criteria [1-2]; however initiation and progression of sub-critical events and their effect on the mechanical response has not been adequately addressed. Furthermore, many applications involve design functions such as structural deflections, vibrations, etc., where critical performance is determined by material stiffness. Design of these structures with strength criteria alone is inaccurate as subcritical damage in form of ply cracking and interfacial debonding occurs well before ultimate failure. Here we present a stiffness based progressive failure modeling approach for multifunctional composite materials. The approach taken here to address this problem is to retain the framework of Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) but enrich its capabilities by combining it with micromechanics. We have called this approach synergistic damage mechanics (SDM). This paper will first briefly describe the SDM methodology and then apply it to selected examples of multidirectional composite laminates. The proposed methodology is being implemented in commercial FEA package ANSYS via user subroutine to enable practical usage.

1 Introduction

Composite materials despite their wide usage are currently designed too conservatively. This conservativeness stems from the use of empirical failure criteria that are extensions of well-known point-based failure analysis for metallic systems.

Furthermore, current design approaches used in composites industry focus solely on strength failure whereas in real applications, depending on the purpose at hand, the failure characteristics may be defined by stiffness characteristics of the composite structure. It is worthy to note that the damage development in polymer composite laminates is quite different from metals and alloys. The damage in laminated composite materials typically begins in the form of multiple matrix cracking in the transverse plies. These ply cracks are *subcritical* in nature, and hence laminates can sustain a large number of such cracks before more *critical* forms of damage such as delamination, fiber fracture can ensue and cause ultimate structural failure. These ply cracks open up and slide during loading and thus result into the loss of stiffness. Understanding how the overall stiffness properties of the composite structure change as a function of applied loading is therefore an important step in developing better failure models that are based on the fundamental mechanistic phenomena of failure in these material systems. An ongoing World-Wide Failure Exercise focuses on the damage mechanics in composite materials [2].

Initial analytical developments to solve the problem of stiffness degradation due to ply cracking consisted of developing and analyzing the boundary value problem (BVP) of composite laminates with ply cracks in transverse plies. Due the complexity of the resulting BVP, these developments were mostly restricted to the case of cross-ply laminates that underwent cracks in the 90° plies only. They varied from one-dimensional *shear lag* approaches [3-4], to the two-dimensional and more accurate *variational* models [5,6]. Later these approaches were extended

to multidirectional laminates; however, they still have severe limitations.

Another approach that has been followed is the so-called *continuum damage mechanics* (CDM) which attempts to bypass solution of the complicated stress BVP and focuses rather on the evaluation of overall stiffness properties of the damaged laminate through the homogenization of damage over a representative volume element (RVE) [7-9]. This approach has been successful for a variety of laminate sequences, but is limited in application due to the need for evaluation of damage constants that require experimental testing. To overcome this limitation, a *synergistic damage mechanics* (SDM) methodology has been recently developed that works not only for cross-ply laminates but also for multidirectional laminates with ply cracks in multiple orientations (or damage modes). More specifically, it has been shown to work for angle-ply ($[\pm\theta/90_4]_s$) laminates with cracks in 90° plies [10], in $[0/\pm\theta_4/0_{1/2}]_s$ laminates with cracks in $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ plies [11], in $[0_m/\pm\theta_n/90_r]_s$ and $[0_m/90_r/\pm\theta_n]_s$ laminates with cracks in 90° , $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ plies [12]. They represent the cases with one damage mode, two damage modes, and three damage modes, respectively. A further improvement in the SDM approach was to include higher order damage terms to accurately predict the nonlinearity in stiffness degradation, consistent with experimental observations. This is being reported in [13]. We are also participating in the WWFE III exercise, and our preliminary results are reported in [14].

An energy based model to predict the evolution of ply crack density with respect to applied loading has been developed in [15]. At the present state, the SDM approach can analyze the development, progression and the effect of subcritical damage for a variety of multidirectional laminates. Nonetheless, its usage into structural analysis has not been attempted. The current work is focused on the development of progressive failure analysis based on the SDM approach and its implementation into commercial finite element packages such as ANSYS and ABAQUS so that it can be used by design engineers for industrial applications.

2 Methodology

Consider a multidirectional composite laminate with a layup that has a mix of on-axis and off-axis (transverse) plies. When such a laminate is loaded in uniaxial tension, damage in form of ply cracks will initiate first in the off-axis plies. Typically they begin with the transverse plies (90°) due to fracture processes in the brittle matrix (polymer) phase. Since these cracks are unstable in nature, they quickly grow and encompass the width and thickness of the given lamina. Assuming self-similarity and equi-spaced nature, the cracks existing in one ply orientation can be grouped together to constitute one damage mode. On further application of load, cracks will initiate and propagate in plies with other off-axis orientations, constituting multiple damage modes. The crack density in different plies keeps increasing until some kind of critical damage state is achieved. If the load is increased further, ply cracks will cause initiation of interlaminar cracking, i.e. delamination at some load value. Delamination, being a critical damage mode can lead to the final failure of the composite structure. Here our focus is on the sub-critical damage, i.e. ply cracking only. The overall role of these intralaminar cracks is to cause a decrease in the load carrying capacity of the whole structure. The relations for stiffness properties of the composite laminate as a function of damage level (i.e. crack density) are described below.

2.1 Damage-stiffness relations

Following the notions of continuum damage mechanics, the effects of damage on mechanical behavior of composite laminate can be analyzed by considering a representative volume element (RVE) around a point containing a set of damage entities. By homogenizing the damage effects over the RVE volume, overall stiffness properties can be derived. For the particular problem of multiple intralaminar cracking, Figure 1 illustrates such an RVE with one set of intralaminar cracks in an off-axis ply of a composite laminate. It is understood that in general ply cracks exist in multiple off-axis plies of the laminate; although the figure shows cracking only in one lamina for the sake of clarity. This damage development consisting of ply cracks in multiple orientations represents a multi-mode damage scenario. For characterizing the effects of this

damage on the overall elastic response of the multidirectional laminate the concepts of CDM approach as developed by Talreja [7,8] are utilized here. As hinted above, the CDM methodology characterizes the ply cracking damage through the homogenization of evolving microstructure involving damage entities over an RVE. The resulting damage field around a point inside material is then described by a second order damage tensor that defines damage state in an equivalent homogenized continuum. Following [9], the damage tensor elements for damage mode α are given by:

$$D_{ij}^{(\alpha)} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{k_\alpha} (d_{ij})_{k_\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where N denotes the number of damage entities, such as microcracks, of the given damage mode in the given RVE, $k_\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and V is the volume of the RVE.

Figure 1: A representative volume element showing intralaminar multiple cracking in a general off-axis ply of a composite laminate.

For the particular case of multiple matrix cracking, the damage mode representing intralaminar cracks in an off-axis ply of orientation θ , can be derived as

$$D_{ij}^{(\alpha)} = \frac{\kappa t_c^2}{st \sin \theta} n_i n_j \quad (2)$$

where $n_i = (\sin \theta, \cos \theta, 0)$ represent the components of normal to the cracked surface. When progressive damage takes place, it reduces the stiffness properties of the whole composite laminate, which can be derived as [12]

$$C_{pq} = C_{pq}^0 + \sum_{\alpha} C_{pq}^{(\alpha)} \quad (3)$$

where C_{pq}^0 is the stiffness matrix for pristine (undamaged) material and $\sum_{\alpha} C_{pq}^{(\alpha)}$ represents the stiffness changes brought about by all the damage modes. The orthotropic stiffness matrix for virgin composite material is given as

$$C_{pq}^0 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x^0}{1-\nu_{xy}^0 \nu_{yx}^0} & \frac{\nu_{xy}^0 E_y^0}{1-\nu_{xy}^0 \nu_{yx}^0} & 0 \\ \frac{E_y^0}{1-\nu_{xy}^0 \nu_{yx}^0} & \frac{\nu_{xy}^0 E_x^0}{1-\nu_{xy}^0 \nu_{yx}^0} & 0 \\ \text{Symm} & & G_{xy}^0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $E_x^0, E_y^0, \nu_{xy}^0, G_{xy}^0$ are effective moduli for the undamaged laminate (calculated using the classical laminate theory). In the following, we would consider different cases representing ply cracking in a single damage mode (90° plies) and three damage modes, respectively. The derivations for following expressions are provided in [11,12,14].

Case 1: Ply cracking in 90° plies only

$$C_{pq}^{(90)} = \frac{\kappa t_c^2}{st} \begin{bmatrix} 2a_1 & a_4 & 0 \\ & 2a_2 & 0 \\ \text{Symm} & & 2a_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $a_i, i = 1, \dots, 4$ are material (laminate) constants to be determined from experimental or computational data on stiffness degradation. It can be observed that the orthotropic symmetry is retained by intralaminar cracking in cross-ply laminates. In the above relations, the constraint

parameter $\kappa = \frac{(\overline{\Delta u_2})}{t_c}$ is the average crack opening displacement normalized with the crack length, i.e. cracked ply thickness. Thus, $(\overline{\Delta u_2})$ and t_c represent the crack opening displacement averaged over the crack surfaces and the thickness of the cracked 90° layer, respectively. Further details on the notations and parameters have been covered previously [12]. The effective damage parameter here is given as $\bar{D} = \frac{\kappa t_c^2}{st}$. The engineering moduli for the cracked laminate can be obtained from the following relationships:

$$E_x = \frac{C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2}{C_{22}} \quad E_y = \frac{C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2}{C_{11}} \quad (6)$$

$$\nu_{xy} = \frac{C_{12}}{C_{22}} \quad G_{xy} = C_{66}$$

Case 2: Multiple damage modes

The details of damage modeling in multidirectional laminates with cracking in multiple off-axis plies are given in references [11-14]. For the special case of $[0_m/90_r/\pm\theta_n]_s$ and $[0_m/\pm\theta_n/90_r]_s$ laminates with intralaminar cracks in $+\theta$, $-\theta$, and 90° layers, the stiffness-damage relations are same as in Eq. (4) except that \bar{D} is now given by [12]

$$\bar{D} = \frac{2t_0^2}{t} \left[\frac{1}{s_n^\theta} \frac{\kappa_\theta}{\kappa_\theta|_{\theta=90}} \left\{ 2(2n+r)^2 \kappa_{90_{4n+2r}} - r^2 \kappa_{90} \right\} + r^2 \frac{\kappa_{90}}{s^{90}} \right] \quad (7)$$

with the constraint parameters defined as

$$\kappa_\theta = \frac{(\overline{\Delta u_2})_{\pm\theta_{4n}}}{4nt_0}; \quad \kappa_{90_{4n+2r}} = \frac{(\overline{\Delta u_2})_{90_{4n+2r}}}{(4n+2r)t_0};$$

$$\kappa_{90} = \frac{(\overline{\Delta u_2})_{90_r}}{rt_0} \quad (8)$$

for $[0_m/90_r/\pm\theta_n]_s$ laminates, and

$$\bar{D} = \frac{4t_0^2}{t} \left[\frac{1}{s_n^\theta} \frac{\kappa_\theta}{\kappa_\theta|_{\theta=90}} \left\{ (2n+r)^2 \kappa_{90_{4n+2r}} - r^2 \kappa_{90} \right\} + r^2 \frac{\kappa_{90}}{s^{90}} \right] \quad (9)$$

with the following constraint parameters

$$\kappa_\theta = \frac{(\overline{\Delta u_2})_{\pm\theta_{2n}}}{2nt_0}; \quad \kappa_{90_{4n+2r}} = \frac{(\overline{\Delta u_2})_{90_{4n+2r}}}{(4n+2r)t_0};$$

$$\kappa_{90} = \frac{(\overline{\Delta u_2})_{90_{2r}}}{2rt_0} \quad (10)$$

Now that the stiffness-damage relations are described for a range of ply sequences, an energy-based model to predict damage evolution is described next.

2.2 Evolution of ply crack density

The evolution of damage can be predicted using a fracture mechanics based energy method utilizing the crack closure concepts. Accordingly, the damage progression from State 1 with N parallel off-axis cracks to State 2 where the cracks have multiplied to $2N$, occurs when the work required in going from State 1 to State 2 exceeds the critical energy release rate, i.e., if

$$W_{2N \rightarrow N} \geq N G_c \cdot \frac{1}{\sin \theta} t_c \quad (11)$$

where G_c is the critical (threshold) value of energy required for ply crack formation within the given laminate. Combining damage progression and stiffness degradation data, the whole stress-strain response of the damaged composite structure is finally obtained.

As described previously in [13], the prediction of crack density evolution requires the use of computational micromechanics in order to evaluate crack surface displacement parameters as a function of crack densities. This can be easily accomplished through finite element analysis, as shown in [13]. The two important parameters are: $\tilde{u}_n^\theta, \tilde{u}_t^\theta$. They represent, respectively, the normalized average crack

opening and sliding displacements (COD and CSD). These are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{u}_n^\theta &= \frac{\bar{u}_n^\theta}{t_c (\sigma_{20}^\theta / E_2)} = \frac{1}{t_c (\sigma_{20}^\theta / E_2)} \int_{-t_c/2}^{t_c/2} u_n(z) dz \\ \tilde{u}_t^\theta &= \frac{\bar{u}_t^\theta}{t_c (\sigma_{120}^\theta / E_2)} = \frac{1}{t_c (\sigma_{120}^\theta / E_2)} \int_{-t_c/2}^{t_c/2} u_t(z) dz\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

where u_n and u_t represent the relative opening and sliding displacement of the cracked surfaces, respectively, and overbars represent averages. For the special case of cracking in 90°-ply only, the sliding displacement is zero (**under uniaxial loading condition**) and hence the criterion for ply multiplication is written as

$$t_c \cdot \frac{(\sigma_{20}^\theta)^2}{E_2} \left[2\tilde{u}_n^\theta \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) - \tilde{u}_n^\theta(s) \right] \geq G_{Ic} \quad (13)$$

where G_{Ic} is the critical energy release rate in Mode I (crack opening mode). For the special case of 90°-cracking in $[S/90_n]_s$ laminates, this relation represents the same expression as derived previously by Joffe et al. [16], except that they consider centrally placed cracked 90°-plies in their model and normalize the average COD with half the ply thickness ($t_c/2$). For cracking in a general off-axis ply, one can use a multi-mode criterion given as

$$\left(\frac{w_I}{G_{Ic}} \right)^M + \left(\frac{w_{II}}{G_{IIc}} \right)^N \geq 1 \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}w_I &= \frac{(\sigma_{20}^\theta)^2 t_c}{E_2} \left[2\tilde{u}_n^\theta \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) - \tilde{u}_n^\theta(s) \right]; \\ w_{II} &= \frac{(\sigma_{120}^\theta)^2 t_c}{E_2} \left[2\tilde{u}_t^\theta \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) - \tilde{u}_t^\theta(s) \right]\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

and G_{IIc} is the critical energy release rate in Mode II (crack sliding mode), and the exponents M and N depend on the material system, for example, for glass/epoxy $M=1$, $N=2$ can be utilized.

In our work [13] we interpreted that the critical material parameters G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} do not conform to the usual linear elastic fracture mechanics sense where they are defined as the resistance to advancement of the crack front at the point of unstable crack growth. Instead, it was postulated that the work required to go from State 1 to State 2 involves a range of dissipative processes that all depend on the material condition in a cracking ply within the given laminate. The material parameter representing the dissipated energy per unit of ply crack surface is, therefore, not what is obtained in a standard fracture toughness test for determining G_{Ic} or G_{IIc} . Furthermore, as discussed in [13], we believe a ply crack cannot form unless sufficient energy is available to open its surfaces (i.e. mode I). In other words, a pure sliding action will not generate a set of parallel cracks which implies that the second term in Eq. (14) is negligible. In fact we report good predictions of crack density evolution by only using the first term in Eq. (14).

3 Results and discussion

For illustration purpose, here we consider $[0_m/90_r/\pm\theta_n]_s$ laminates. On longitudinal tensile loading, progressive damage in the form of multiple matrix cracking will evolve in the 90°, + θ and - θ plies. If we take $\theta = 45^\circ$, it becomes a quasi-isotropic laminate. For these laminate sequences, the cracks will form in all 90, +45 and -45 orientations in plies with those orientations. Figure 3 demonstrates that the ply cracks first form in the 90°-ply at about 0.5% axial strain. After load is increased, ply cracks also initiate in 45°-plies at the 90/45 ply interfaces. They not only cause damage by themselves, but also lead to increase in the 90°-ply crack density.

The predictions for stiffness reduction (longitudinal Young's modulus), and damage progression (evolution of crack density) using the SDM approach for a quasi-isotropic laminate, are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. From the figures, it can be clearly seen that the SDM approach compares well with experimental data. Initially the stiffness degradation is due to the 90°-ply cracks. However, when 45°-cracks also initiate, they not only cause degradation in stiffness but also add to increase in the crack density and crack opening

displacements in the 90-ply. This is evident on looking both figures in conjunction. Hence, a multi-mode scenario would typically tend to be more detrimental than just the linear addition of individual damages. Further results, including stress-strain curves subsequent to damage development for a variety of laminate types and material systems are described in [14].

Figure 2: Comparison of SDM predictions for stiffness degradation in for quasi-isotropic composite laminates with experimental data. Source: [12].

Figure 3: Comparison of SDM predictions for evolution of ply crack density in quasi-isotropic laminates as a function of applied axial strain with experimental data. Source: [13].

A key limitation of the CDM and SDM approaches has been that they predict linear stiffness

degradation over the whole range of crack densities. This is against available experimental data which overwhelmingly shows that as crack density increases the rate of stiffness degradation reduces leading to a saturation behavior. This is because the uncracked plies provide a minimum level of stiffness for the whole laminate. To overcome this limitation, the damage characterization must involve higher order damage terms in the energy from which the constitutive laws are derived. This is accomplished in our most recent paper [15]. The corresponding stiffness-damage predictions performed for angle ply, off-axis and quasi-isotropic laminate configurations show significant improvement in accuracy of SDM predictions at large crack densities.

Now we describe the method to predict stress-strain response of a damaged laminate under uniaxial tensile loading. The procedure begins by identifying the crack initiation strain for a given laminate type and layup using the Eqns. (13)-(15). Thereafter, the crack density evolution is obtained from these expressions as a function of applied strain, i.e.

$$\rho = \rho(\epsilon) \tag{16}$$

The stiffness properties of the damaged laminate are then evaluated using SDM expressions in Section 3, leading to

$$C = C_0 + \Delta C(\rho) \tag{17}$$

Subsequently, the stress-strain response of the whole laminate is evaluated using the FE code. For the case of quasi-isotropic laminates, the predicted stress-strain plot is shown in Figure 4. The cases of undamaged laminate, damaged with cracks only in the 90°-plies, with cracks in both 90° and 45° plies are depicted. Since, the 45°-cracks may not develop fully through the lamina thickness and width, an effective normalized density with respect to 90°-plies is considered, with two sub-cases – one representing the case when 45°-cracks occupy 1/4th of the area of cracks when fully grown, and another with 45°-cracks occupying half of this area. These bounds are consistent with experimental observations. The variation of the overall effective longitudinal modulus of the damaged laminate as a function of applied strain is displayed in Figure 5. It

can be easily seen that the stiffness decreases very quickly early on damage initiation, but saturates out at large crack densities due to inherent stiffness contribution from the uncracked 0° -plies.

Figure 4: Predicted stress-strain response of quasi-isotropic laminates with cracks in 90° , and 45° -plies.

Figure 5: Variation of the longitudinal stiffness modulus as a function of applied strain for damaged quasi-isotropic laminate with ply cracks in 90° and 45° -plies.

Until now the focus has been the development of CDM and SDM methodologies for a variety of multidirectional laminates. For wider usage, these techniques must be implemented in commercial FE packages, such as ANSYS. Here we describe a brief overview of the procedure that is being implemented in the code through subroutine for user defined material (**usermat**). The anticipated challenges and

the limitations of our model are also highlighted. Currently, the methodology is focused on the uniaxial tensile loading only. The calculations for predicting stress-strain response are conducted through Eqns. (16) and (17).

The computational modeling effort so far has focused on failure prediction based on the sub-critical damage in form of ply cracking only. However, often the damage scenario in real applications may involve both sub-critical and critical damage mechanisms simultaneously. Since both subcritical and critical damage mechanisms contribute to the non-linear stress strain response of the material, the present model needs to be extended to include these damage mechanisms for prediction of final failure as described below:

1. Ply cracking: Cracking if criterion in Eq. (14) is satisfied. Then, follow Eqs. (16)-(17). When stiffness of damaged laminate falls below a “designed” limit, final failure is assumed to occur.
2. Delamination: For delaminations growing out of off-axis ply cracks, a model such as the one developed in [17] can be utilized. However, this model is applicable only for cross-ply laminates; hence its usage for multidirectional laminates is questionable. A way to circumvent this issue could be to consider a crack density level as which delamination initiation could be assumed.
3. Fiber fracture: When applied strain exceeds failure strain of a longitudinal (0°) lamina.
4. Fiber microbuckling: Under compressive or multi-axial loading, fibers can undergo microbuckling. This can be modeled using previously developed criteria by other researchers, e.g. [18].

If the progressive cracking begins through ply cracking damage mode, as is the case in general, the design criterion for failure should be such that only a certain level of reduction in the load bearing capability of the composite structure is allowed. If the stiffness properties fall below this limit, the composite structure should be assumed to have failed. This is the main focus of our progressive failure model. For multi-axial loading cases, other damage mechanisms would also be implemented along with the ply cracking SDM approach.

4 Conclusions

Progressive failure in multidirectional composite laminates begins through the process of multiple matrix cracking with increasing damage levels as well cracking occurring in multiple off-axis plies. A direct impact of this damage is to reduce the overall stiffness properties of the complete structure. In this work, this effect is characterized through the newly developed synergistic damage mechanics methodology which combines computational micromechanics with continuum damage mechanics. As detailed in our recently published papers, the SDM approach works well for various ply cracking scenarios. Here, preliminary ideas regarding the implementation of this model into commercial finite element package ANSYS are detailed. Some simple example applications such as composite plate with different ply layups and plate with a hole will be highlighted in the conference.

Although the basic ideas towards implementation of progressive failure prediction using SDM technique have been described above, many challenges and issues remain unresolved. First, the non-uniformity of crack densities around complex shapes such as for plate with a hole needs to be accounted for in the modeling framework. Then the ply cracking based model needs to be combined with other damage mechanisms. Next, the challenge of multi-axial loading needs to be characterized. FE implementation also needs careful attention as the material behavior would be mesh-dependent subsequent to a significant loss in elastic properties due to damage. Our focus will be to overcome these challenges in the near future and lead to a successful code that can predict progressive failure of composite structure in a physically consistent manner.

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